

OXYFLUOBORATES. PART III. AMMINO AND ORGANIC AMINO
COMPLEXES OF COPPER, CADMIUM, ZINC AND NICKEL
OXYFLUOBORATES

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Oxyfluoborates of copper, cadmium, zinc and nickel give ammino and organic amino complexes, similar in nature to those of the corresponding sulphates. The isolation of the above complexes shows that the oxyfluoborate anion is stable also in ammoniacal medium.

Sulphates of copper, cadmium, zinc and nickel form ammino complexes of the general formula $[M(NH_3)_n]SO_4$. With nickel the hexammino complex, being more stable than the tetrammino one, is obtained more easily. Werner *et al.* (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1893, 3, 267) prepared quite a large number of organic amino complexes of metal sulphates like Cu, Ni, etc. Similar work has been carried out with fluoberyllates of these elements by N. Ray and co-workers (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 221; 1955, 32, 209).

Oxyfluoborates of the above elements also give similar stable ammino and organic amino complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tetrammino-cupric Oxyfluoborate Monohydrate.—To a concentrated solution of copper oxyfluoborate in water an equal volume of liquor ammonia was added with constant stirring. The temperature of the solution was kept below 10° by means of ice and salt. Through the deep blue solution gaseous ammonia was passed below 10° for about half an hour. The resulting solution was kept in a caustic soda desiccator in an atmosphere of ammonia. The dark blue crystals obtained after a few days were filtered, washed with alcohol containing a little ammonia, dried between the folds of a filter paper and finally dried in a desiccator over lime in an atmosphere of ammonia. {Found: Cu, 27.00; NH_3 , 29.00; F, 24.28. $[Cu(NH_3)_4BF_3O.H_2O]$ requires Cu, 27.24; NH_3 , 29.14; F, 24.41%}. These crystals may be preserved without decomposition at a low temperature and in a dry atmosphere. When exposed to moist air, it undergoes decomposition with liberation of ammonia.

Tetrammino-cadmium oxyfluoborate was obtained in the same way as the copper compound. The white crystals were first washed with alcohol and then with ether, both saturated with ammonia. Then it was dried between the folds of a filter paper and finally in a desiccator over lime. {Found: Cd, 42.05; NH_3 , 25.45 $[Cd(NH_3)_4] \cdot BOF_3$ requires Cd, 42.54; NH_3 , 25.74%}.

Tetrammino-zinc Oxyfluoborate.—The colorless crystals of the compound were obtained in the same way as above. This compound is fairly stable in dry atmosphere but unstable in moist atmosphere. {Found: Zn, 30.05; NH_3 , 31.26; F, 25.91. $[Zn(NH_3)_4] \cdot BOF_3$ requires Zn, 30.10; NH_3 , 31.31; F, 26.24%}.

Hexammino-nickel Oxyfluoborate.—The violet crystals of the compound were filtered under suction, washed with alcohol and then with ether, both saturated with ammonia. Finally the compound was dried in a desiccator over lime in an atmosphere of ammonia. {Found: Ni, 23.80; N, 34.00; B, 4.26. $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{BOF}_3$ requires Ni, 24.00; N, 34.35; B, 4.42%}. It loses ammonia when kept over sulphuric acid or when exposed to moist air; on heating to a comparatively low temperature rapid evolution of ammonia occurs.

Hexammino-nickel Oxyfluoborate Potassium Iodide.—To a concentrated solution of hexammino nickel oxyfluoborate, cooled by ice and salt, a saturated solution of potassium iodide containing ammonia was added. A light violet-coloured microcrystalline powder separated. It was filtered, washed and dried as before. {Found: I, 43.78; F, 9.66. $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{BOF}_3 \cdot 2\text{KI}$ requires I, 44.02; F, 9.88%}. The compound on exposure to air slowly loses ammonia and gradually turns green.

tris-Ethylenediamine-nickel Oxyfluoborate.—100% Ethylenediamine was added to a saturated solution of nickel oxyfluoborate with constant stirring, kept below 5° by means of ice and salt. A violet precipitate was obtained after a few minutes. It was filtered under suction, washed with 60% alcohol containing some ethylenediamine and dried thoroughly by pressing between the folds of a filter paper. {Found: Ni, 18.00; N, 25.90; F, 17.48. $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3]\text{BOF}_3$ requires Ni, 18.19; N, 26.08; F, 17.67%}. These violet crystals are sparingly soluble in cold water, but are decomposed by hot water. The crystals are stable under ordinary conditions.

tris-Propylenediamine-nickel Oxyfluoborate.—70% Propylenediamine was added dropwise with constant stirring to a saturated solution of nickel oxyfluoborate which was kept at or below 10° by means of ice and salt. The violet precipitate obtained was washed with alcohol containing some propylenediamine and dried between the folds of a filter paper. {Found: Ni, 15.96; N, 22.85; B, 2.68. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_3]\text{BOF}_3$ requires Ni, 16.10; N, 23.05; B, 2.96%}. This violet compound is sparingly soluble in cold water. On boiling, a suspension of the compound in water undergoes decomposition with the precipitation of nickel hydroxide. It is quite stable under ordinary conditions.

Hexamethylenetetramine-nickel Oxyfluoborate.—To a saturated solution of nickel oxyfluoborate was added a saturated solution of hexamethylenetetramine, kept at or below 10° by means of ice and salt. On stirring, the colour of the solution gradually faded and shining pale green crystals were obtained. These were washed with 60% alcohol until free of excess of hexamethylenetetramine and then dried in air. (Found: Ni, 12.96; N, 12.40; F, 12.51. $\text{NiBOF}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 13.23; N, 12.59; F, 12.84%). The crystals are soluble in water but not in alcohol.

bis-Ethylenediamine-copper oxyfluoborate was obtained by adding ethylenediamine monohydrate to a saturated solution of copper oxyfluoborate, cooled in ice and salt. Addition of ethylenediamine was stopped just before the colour of the solution had turned reddish violet. It was kept in a vacuum desiccator over caustic soda. After a few days blue crystals were obtained, which were washed with alcohol containing some ethylenediamine, and dried in air. {Found: Cu, 18.10; N, 15.84; F, 15.88.

[Cu en₂]BOF₃.4½H₂O requires Cu, 18.25 ; N, 16.07 ; F, 16.30% }. It may be recalled that the corresponding sulphate also crystallises with 4½ molecules of water, whereas the corresponding fluoboryllate crystallises with 4 molecules of water.

tris-Ethylenediamine-copper oxyfluoborate pentahydrate was obtained in the same way as above. The addition of ethylenediamine was continued until the colour of the solution became deep reddish violet. It was then allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator over caustic soda. After a few days, deep blue crystals were obtained which were washed with 80% alcohol, and dried in air. { Found: Cu, 15.15 ; N, 19.94 ; F, 13.32. [Cu en₂]BOF₃.5H₂O requires Cu, 15.23 ; N, 20.13 ; F, 13.60% }.

tris-Ethylenediamine-copper oxyfluoborate was obtained by adding anhydrous ethylenediamine to a saturated solution of copper oxyfluoborate, cooled in ice and salt. The addition of ethylenediamine was continued until the colour of the solution became dark red. This on crystallisation in a vacuum desiccator over caustic soda gave deep blue crystals. These were washed with 80% alcohol containing a little anhydrous ethylenediamine, and dried in air. { Found: Cu, 19.30 ; N, 25.40 ; F, 17.08. [Cu en₂]BOF₃ requires Cu, 19.41 ; N, 25.65 ; F, 17.34% }. This substance is slightly hygroscopic.

tris-Propylenediamine-copper oxyfluoborate was obtained in the same way as in the case of tris-ethylene compound. An excess of propylenediamine (70%) was added to a saturated solution of copper oxyfluoborate, cooled in ice and salt. It was crystallised and washed as usual.

It is a deep blue hygroscopic substance, highly soluble in water. { Found: Cu, 13.70 ; N, 18.00 ; F, 12.08. [Cu pn₂]BOF₃.5H₂O requires Cu, 13.84 ; N, 18.29 ; F, 12.36% }.

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